

TRAINING PROGRAM FOR SELF-READINESS AND PEDAGOGICAL PREPAREDNESS OF ELEMENTARY TEACHERS IN PRIVATE SCHOOLS

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Training Program for Self-Readiness and Pedagogical Preparedness of Elementary Teachers in Private Schools

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Abstract

This study determined the level of self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private schools and develop a training program for the upskilling and reskilling of teachers. Research and Development was employed. Weighted mean and Pearson r were used in achieving valid results. The study used sets of survey questionnaire which were validated and tested for the reliability level by the experts using the computed mean and Cronbach alpha. Based on the results of the study, the level of self-readiness of elementary teachers in private schools in terms of physical readiness, emotional readiness, experiential readiness and knowledge readiness is Very High and the level pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private schools in terms of delivery and instructions, assessment of learning, learning resources, and learning support is High. The results also revealed that there is a significant relationship between the level of readiness and pedagogical preparedness of teachers in full implementation of face-to-face class in the elementary department. The results were used by the researcher to develop a training program for readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private schools which were validated by the experts in the field. It is highly recommended that teachers utilize the developed program for them to be guided in their teaching profession.

Keywords: *pedagogical preparedness, private schools, self-readiness, training program*

Introduction

The unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic has abruptly changed many facets of the global civilization, including the education sector, which has witnessed some unexpected academic shifts in many different corners of the world. For the first time in educational history, COVID-19 compelled schools all over the world, and in the Philippines in particular, there was an abrupt academic shift from frontal teaching in classrooms to distance learning.

The Philippines is one of the countries that has been most severely affected by the virus. The standard of education in the nation is one of the most affected regions. To consistently provide high-quality and accessible instruction for all learners across all learning levels, the technical education and skills development authority, the commission on higher education, and the department of education have collaborated to develop strategies for the educational sector (Jamon, 2021).

Private schools have played a crucial part in the education of young Filipinos, and they are essential to ensure the availability of high-quality educational services. They operate in accordance with DepEd's laws and regulations and use the same curriculum as the public schools. Even though private schools generally have lower class numbers and better facilities and resources, wealthy parents still send their children there even if public schools are practically free. Private basic education institutions in the Philippines are extremely important in forming young Filipinos' perceptions of high-quality services (Acidre, 2019).

All private basic education schools must administer their educational programs in accordance with DepEd standards, which are enforced by the Bureau of Private Schools (BPS), which was created by House Bill 4813. The bureau conducts research, develops prototype curricular designs, and makes recommendations to improve the curricula provided by private schools. All the initiatives and actions of for-profit educational institutions are still under the control of DepEd. The situation has also affected the elementary teachers in private schools of General Santos City. They need to conduct reorientation and trainings about face-to-face class amidst unprecedented Covid-19 pandemic and mostly newly hired teachers are fresh graduate which is during their practice teaching is through online class. Readiness and preparedness of teachers in teaching classes is important so that they can improve teaching skills to successfully guide learners' learning. It enhances student learning and performance to give learners more opportunities to acquire knowledge and potentially improve the performance.

For the school year 2022–2023, the Department of Education mandated face-to-face instruction in both public and private schools. According to the Department of Education, private schools in the country are allowed to continue with blended learning—both distance learning and face-to-face classes in the Philippines combined, even after November 2 until the end of the school year 2023. The Department of Education is fully aware of the impacts of the pandemic on private sectors—from investing in online technologies for online learning and institutionalization of practices on blended learning to the closure of some small private schools due to losses.

This study focused on determining the self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private schools within General Santos City. The researcher determined the teachers' level of readiness, the level of preparedness, the assessment of a significant relationship between the level of readiness and the level of preparedness, and the training program designed is based on the results. In order to do so, the researcher conducted in-person surveys among elementary teachers in three (3) private schools. The data

collected by the researcher is analyzed determining whether the teachers are ready for the new normal of education. With this, teachers go above and beyond in order ensure learners' safety during the unprecedented Covid-19 pandemic and to make learning more meaningful, interesting, and interactive. For learners to feel safe while learning, teachers also encourage and motivate them to accept the new norm in education. Therefore, it is important to look into the situation of private education in nation.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private schools of General Santos City for the School Year 2024-2025. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of self-readiness of teachers in full implementation of face-face classes in the elementary department in terms of:
 - 1.1. physical readiness;
 - 1.2. emotional readiness;
 - 1.3. experiential readiness; and
 - 1.4. knowledge readiness?
2. What is the level of pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in full implementation of face-face classes in the elementary department in terms of:
 - 2.1. delivery and instruction;
 - 2.2. assessment of learning;
 - 2.3. learning support; and
 - 2.4. learning resources?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private school in full implementation of face-to-face class in terms of:
 - 3.1. delivery and instruction;
 - 3.2. assessment of learning
 - 3.3. learning support; and
 - 3.4. learning resources?
4. Based on the results, what training program can be developed?
5. What is the validity level of the designed training program in terms of
 - 4.1. acceptability;
 - 4.2. appropriateness;
 - 4.3. content;
 - 4.4. relevance; and
 - 4.5. usability?

Methodology

Research Design

This is a research and development design, specifically the development research. It involves different stages named the R and D cycle. Borg and Gall, enumerated the different stages as, studying the research findings related to the product to be developed, field testing in the setting where it was intended for use and revising for improvement purposes. It is a systematic study of designing study of designing, developing and evaluating instructional programs, processes and products that meet the criteria of internal consistency and effectiveness.

Also, to ascertain the significant relationship between the level of self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness among elementary teachers in the private schools specifically the members of the Private School of Basic Education Association (PSBEA) full implementation of face-to-face class for the School Year 2024–2025, the researcher used a descriptive-correlational design. This strategy is applied when two variables are associated with one another, claims Calmorin (2005).

Respondents

The respondents are the elementary teachers in three (3) private schools specifically the Private School of Basic Education Association (PSBEA) in General Santos City for the 2023-2024 academic year. Purposive sampling is a sort of non-probability selection in which researchers use their own decision to select members of the public to take part in their surveys. It is also referred to as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. There will be thirty-three (33) elementary school teachers that will participate in the study as respondents.

Instruments

In this study, the instruments used by the researchers were questionnaires to primarily gather data and supply the information needed for the study.

The questionnaire consists of two (2) parts: Part I. Level of Self-Readiness of Teachers, Part II. Level of Pedagogical Preparedness of Teachers

Part I. Self-Readiness of Teachers. There are four subcategories of teacher ready: knowledge readiness, experiential readiness, emotional readiness, and physical readiness. These are assessed using a 5-point Likert scale, with the respondents' stated behaviors and comments serving as the basis for determining how ready they are. Very high, high, moderately high, low, and very low are all options on the scale. "Very high" denotes the teacher respondent's level of assurance and certainty regarding his or her readiness in terms of understanding and knowledge of the questionnaire's indicators. The teacher response on the following scale, "High," has taken readiness into account considering the current situation and has engaged in ready activities to advance knowledge and practices. "Moderately high" is the next response on the scale, which denotes neutrality or a position in the middle between agreement and disagreement. "Low" indicates that the teacher respondent is unsure of how ready he or she would be if put into practice, and "Very low" indicates that there was no preparation at all.

Part II. Pedagogical Preparedness. The four subcategories of teacher preparedness are delivery and teaching, learning assessment, learning resources, and learning support. These are assessed using a 5-point Likert scale, with the respondents' stated behaviors and comments serving as the basis for determining how prepared they are. "Very high" "high," "moderately high," "low," and "very low" are the options on the scale. By selecting "Very high," a teacher indicates that he or she is confident in their level of readiness about their comprehension and familiarity with the indications listed in the questionnaire. The teacher response on the following scale, "high," has made preparations in light of the current situation and has engaged in preparatory efforts to advance knowledge and practices. The next option on the scale is "moderately high," which indicates that the teacher respondent is unsure of his or her preparations if they are implemented and that the knowledge gained regarding the applicability of the indicators as stated in this study. The option "low" is the next option, which indicates that the teacher respondent is unsure of his or her preparations if they are implemented and that the knowledge gained is not certain. The said questionnaires will be carefully validated by the experiments.

Procedure

In conducting the research, the following steps were observed:

The principal of the selected private schools in General Santos City received a letter of permission from the researcher. Once approved, a letter of request forwarded to the academic coordinator that their teachers would be the respondents. The researcher would wait an update from the academic coordinator for the schedule of administering the survey questionnaires. When the schedule was given, the researcher would immediately conduct the survey to the respondents. The researcher would personally administer the survey questionnaires so that the questions arising during the conduct would immediately attended by the researcher.

After the successful gathering of data, the weighted mean would be used to analyze the level of self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private school in the full implementation of face-to-face class. Pearson-r would be used for the identification of significant relationship between the level of self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of the elementary teachers to the delivery of instruction, assessment of learning, learning support, and learning resources. The researcher developed a training program for the elementary teachers in private school in General Santos City based on the quantitative data generated from the study. The program validated by the school principal of the private school. To determined the level of validity of the Training Program for Self-Readiness and Pedagogical Preparedness of Elementary Teachers in Private Schools in terms of its acceptability, appropriateness, content, relevance and usability weighted mean would be used.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers made certain that all ethical considerations were followed as mandatory by the Holy Trinity College Ethical to avoid engaging in practices that may implicitly or explicitly abuse or exploit those with whom he/she sought to conduct research with.

Informed Consent. We used informed consent to ensure that all of the data and information we collected had permission and full participation before beginning the study. We sought the approval of our lecturer, the dean of the college of teacher's education at Holy Trinity College in General Santos City, and the school president. When we were given the go-ahead to conduct our study in their school, we wrote a letter of validation. We reach out to potential participants and ask them to participate in our study.

Voluntary Participation. This study participant must voluntarily participate in order to avoid any sort of coercion or pressure. Every participant is free to stop participating in the study at any time without feeling obligated to do so

Data Privacy. We adhered to the DNA, or the Data Privacy Act, to ensure that the information about our participants was private and protected. And we make sure that everyone who participates in our study is comfortable doing so. We treat everyone equally, regardless of their gender or ethnic background. There won't be any prejudice or discrimination in the interview procedure for this study.

Gender Sensitivity. This study looks at how gender concerns are taken into account when doing research to avoid gender discrimination. While conducting our research, we take into account the equality of all genders as well as the similarities between each man and woman in pre-service teachers' experiences and opinions during the transitional period. These pre-service teachers' experiences and opinions, both male and female, are crucial to our research. We also understand that gender-sensitive planning uses specific techniques and

devices to give both men and women more opportunities for participation.

Cultural Sensitivity. Cultural sensitivity is the first step towards cultural competency. It is the recognition and respect individuals from other cultures, cultural sensitivity is a crucial concern.

Results and Discussion

Level of Self-Readiness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes of Elementary Teachers in Private Schools

Table 1.1 shows the findings of the study on the level of self-readiness of teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in the elementary department in private schools in terms of physical readiness.

Table 1.1. *Level of Self-readiness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes in the Elementary department in terms of Physical Readiness*

	<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	I am physically healthy to teach.	4.52	Very High
2.	I am Covid-19 fully vaccinated.	4.88	Very High
3.	I am aware of safety protocols and precautions.	4.91	Very High
4.	I am oriented with the proper health protocols to avoid spreading the virus.	4.94	Very High
5.	I know that I am not allowed to go to school when I am not feeling well.	4.88	Very High
	Overall Mean	4.83	Very High

The table shows that the item with the highest computed mean of 4.94 described as Very High states that teachers are aware with the proper health protocols to avoid spreading the virus. Teachers are aware of safety protocols and precautions has a computed mean of 4.91 which is described as Very High. Teachers are Covid-19 fully vaccinated. Teachers are physically healthy to teach has computed mean of 4.52 which is described as Very High. Given an overall mean of 4.83, the extent of the level of self-readiness of elementary teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in private schools in terms of physical readiness.

These imply that the teachers in the elementary department in private schools display a very high level of self-readiness in the full implementation of face-to-face classes. This collective readiness bodes well for the safe and effective resumption of in-person teaching, highlighting the teachers' conscientiousness towards health and safety measures necessary for the well-being of the school community. According to Quinn and Seligman (2019) teacher well-being is a crucial issue for school and society. It is seen as relating to teaching effectiveness, learners' outcomes and educational governance.

Table 1.2 present the self-perceived emotional readiness of elementary school teachers for the full implementation of face-to-face classes. This table focuses on the emotional aspects that contribute to their readiness to resume in-person teaching. Across various parameters surveyed, the teachers consistently displayed a high level of emotional preparedness.

Table 1.2. *Level of Self-readiness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes in the Elementary department in terms of Emotional Readiness*

	<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	I am comfortable with face-to-face classes.	4.76	Very High
2.	I am confident about the task during face-to-face classes.	4.70	Very High
3.	I am excited to be in class during face-to-face classes.	4.58	Very High
4.	I am more determined to comply with the requirement and task in school.	4.58	Very High
5.	I feel active in teaching full face-to-face classes.	4.61	Very High
	Overall Mean	4.65	Very High

It was found out that elementary teachers in private schools are comfortable with face-to-face classes to Very High extent given a computed mean of 4.76; they are confident about the task during face-to-face classes with a computed mean of 4.70 which is also described as to Very High extent. On the other hand, the items with the lowest computed mean of 4.58 as to Very High is that teachers are excited to be in class during face-to-face classes and more determined to comply with the requirements and tasks in school. Generally, the extent of the level of self-readiness of elementary teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in private schools in terms of emotional readiness is Very High an overall computed mean of 4.65.

This emotional readiness signifies a strong foundation for a successful transition back to in-person teaching, reflecting the teachers' positive mindset and eagerness to deliver quality education in a traditional classroom setting.

According to Diener (2020), positive emotions and the ability to maintain emotional balance help people cope with situations of extreme stress and effectively manage day-to-day routine teaching processes when deciding what and how to teach. Emotional readiness contributes to positive teacher-student relationships cooperative classroom environments positively impacts teachers' emotional well-being and professional lives in general. At the organizational level positive emotions can be significant in maintaining a stable staff, enhancing teachers' commitment to the organization, and reducing instances of teachers intending to leave school. Emotional readiness can therefore be considered a psychological factor that can strengthen teachers' well-being and their relationship with the organization.

Another aspect of emotional readiness and its link to well-being and intention to leave is its role as a mediating psychological factor in the relationship between job and personal resources with well-being and intention to leave. To our knowledge, the role of emotional readiness as a mediator in the context of the problem under investigation has not been explored in detail.

Table 1.3 outlines the self-assessed experiential readiness of elementary school teachers for the full implementation of face-to-face classes. This table focuses on the teachers' perceived ability to adapt their teaching methods and effectively navigate the classroom environment in the current educational landscape. The results suggest a strong level of readiness in several key areas.

Table 1.3. *Level of Self-readiness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes in the Elementary department in terms of Experiential Readiness*

Items	Mean	Description
1. I can apply the teaching strategies I used before the pandemic in the current set-up.	4.36	High
2. I can deliver my topics well the same as before the pandemic.	4.45	High
3. I can relate my personal experiences to connect in discussions.	4.67	Very High
4. I can use both traditional and modern way of teaching.	4.73	Very High
5. I am driven to achieve short and long-term goals.	4.64	Very High
Overall Mean	4.57	Very High

The table reveals that the item with the highest computed mean of 4.73 described as Very High states that the teachers can use both traditional and modern way of teaching. The item that mentions that teachers can relate their personal experiences to connect in discussions has a computed mean of 4.64 described as Very High. However, the items the lowest computed mean 4.36 described as High is that the teachers can apply teaching strategies they used before the pandemic in the current set-up. Hence, the given overall mean of 4.57, the extent of level of self-readiness of elementary teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in private schools in terms of experiential readiness is described as Very High.

This readiness underscores their ability to navigate the complexities of the evolving educational landscape, showcasing a blend of adaptability, versatility, and commitment to effective teaching practices in a face-to-face setting.

According to the US National Council on Teacher Quality (2017), the professional development of teachers over the years has been designed to provide teachers with knowledge, skills, and teaching methods through high-quality interactive experiences. It is focused on how to enhance classroom practices, which is a concern for the quality of teaching and learning in schools. Soslau and Raths (2017) aver that only entry-level knowledge and skills cannot sustain teachers' classroom practices in a dynamic society, but regular professional development can appropriately support the modern education system. Teaching experiences from the initial teacher education they join the profession with are insufficient to maintain quality in education, studies have established that teachers are often confronted with efficient delivery of curriculum and materials development (Sarıçoban, 2010).

Teaching experiences from the initial teacher education and they join the profession with are insufficient to maintain quality in education, studies have established that teachers are often confronted with efficient delivery of curriculum and materials development. The integration of experiential learning theory is to make their professional development experiential- based activities and allow teachers to construct learning experiences for their learner as transformative learning experiences, O'Dowd and Dooly (2022).

Table 1.4 presents the self-reported knowledge readiness of elementary school teachers for the full implementation of face-to-face classes. This table emphasizes the teachers' perceived proficiency in employing different teaching strategies, engaging learners, conducting effective teaching and learning processes, and their breadth of subject knowledge.

The item with the highest computed mean of 4.64 described as Very High states that teachers have knowledge to conduct teaching and learning processes. They have variety of preferred existing styles of learning has a computed mean of 4.52 which is described as Very High. They have the approaches to draw the attention of learners has the lowest computed mean of 4.39 which is described as High. Given an overall mean of 4.50, the extent of level of self-readiness of elementary teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in private schools in terms of knowledge readiness is described as Very High.

Table 1.4. *Level of Self-readiness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes in the Elementary department in terms of Knowledge Readiness*

Items	Mean	Description
1. I have the knowledge to use various teaching strategies.	4.48	High
2. I have the knowledge to use various approaches to draw the attention of learners.	4.39	High
3. I have the knowledge to conduct teaching and learning processes.	4.64	Very High
4. I have knowledge in teaching different subjects.	4.45	High
5. I have variety of preferred existing styles of learning.	4.52	Very High
Overall Mean	4.50	Very High

This readiness highlights their proficiency in employing diverse teaching strategies, maintaining learner engagement, conducting effective teaching processes, and catering to varied learning styles, thereby contributing to a conducive and enriched classroom environment. According to the US National Council on Teacher Quality (2020), the professional development of teachers over the

years has been designed to provide teachers with knowledge, skills and teaching methods through high-quality interactive experiences. It is focused on how to enhance classroom practices, which is a concern for the quality of teaching and learning in schools. Teachers' knowledge influences children's cognitive development. The biggest influence on child development and learning came from teachers' knowledge on child learning.

Table 1.5. *Summary Results on Level of Self-readiness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes in the Elementary department*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Physical Readiness	4.83	Very High
2.	Emotional Readiness	4.65	Very High
3.	Experiential Readiness	4.57	Very High
4.	Knowledge Readiness	4.50	Very High
	Over-all Mean	4.64	Very High

Based on the computed mean, of level of self-readiness of elementary teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in private schools of all indicators were Very High. Physical readiness has a computed mean of 4.83; emotional readiness has a computed mean of 4.65; experiential readiness has a computed mean of 4.57; and, knowledge readiness has a computed mean of 4.50 resulting to an overall computed mean of 4.64 described as Very High.

These findings suggest a collective confidence and readiness among educators, laying a solid foundation for a successful and conducive return to in-person teaching environments, ensuring the well-being and quality education of learners. It is teachers' responsibility to take initiatives in maintaining pupils' passion and motivation by applying various meaningful techniques and approaches in teaching and learning (Iberahim, Mahamod & Mohamad, 2020). Effective teaching approaches play an important part in increasing pupils' ability to master knowledge and skills they required.

Level of Pedagogical Preparedness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes of Elementary Teachers in Private Schools

Table 2.1 shows the findings of the study on the level of pedagogical preparedness of teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in the elementary department in private schools in terms of physical readiness.

Table 2.1. *Level of Pedagogical Preparedness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes in terms of Delivery and Instruction*

	<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	I design learning activities that provide opportunities for learners' interactions.	4.45	High
2.	I provide instructional support any time during the day of learning activities.	4.45	High
3.	I support my lesson with presentations and videos.	4.42	High
4.	I provide instructional support alternatives to those learners with learning difficulties.	4.39	High
5.	I provide feedback at the end of each learning week.	4.36	High
	Overall Mean	4.41	High

The table shows that the items with the highest computed mean of 4.45 described as High states that teachers can design learning activities that provide opportunities for learners' interaction and can provide instructional support any time during the day of learning activities. They can support their lessons with presentations and videos has a computed mean of 4.42 which is described as High. They can provide feedback at the end of each learning week has the lowest computed mean and 4.36 which is described as High. Given an overall mean of 4.41, the extent of level of pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in private schools in terms of delivery and instructions is described as High.

This preparedness implies their confidence and capability in creating engaging learning activities, offering support, utilizing multimedia resources, catering to diverse learning needs, and providing feedback to foster a conducive learning environment. These preparedness measures indicate a strong foundation for effective face-to-face teaching in the elementary department, ensuring a comprehensive and supportive learning experience for learners.

Norazman, Nor'ain and Nur-Fazliana (2021), study showed that teachers must be smart in delivering their lessons, have content knowledge of their subject matter and be highly creative so that the learning environment is conducive. Teachers have to put in effort so the learners do not continuously perform unsatisfactorily. The study recommends that teachers should take steps to overcome their weaknesses in different aspects such as teaching, assessment, subject matter or guidance given to learners.

Table 2.2 showcases the pedagogical preparedness of elementary school teachers for the full implementation of face-to-face classes concerning the Assessment of Learning. This table highlights teachers' perceived abilities in evaluating and measuring learners' understanding and progress.

The items with the highest computed mean of 4.67 described as Very High states that teachers can create written and performance

assessment tools. Teachers can use different platforms to conduct question and answer activity to validate learners' understanding of the lesson has a computed mean of 4.64 which is described as Very High. They can use different types of assessment to measure the learning of the learners which has the lowest computed mean of 4.48 as described as High. Given an overall mean of 4.59, the extent of level of pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in private schools in terms of assessment of learning is described as Very High.

Table 2.2. *Level of Pedagogical Preparedness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes in terms of Assessment of Learning*

Items	Mean	Description
I create written and performance assessment tools.	4.67	Very High
I use different platforms to conduct question and answer activity to validate learners' understanding of the lesson.	4.64	Very High
I create different group and individual activities.	4.55	Very High
I provide learner activity sheets to evaluate learning activities.	4.61	Very High
I use different types of assessment to measure the learning of the learners.	4.48	High
Overall Mean	4.59	Very High

This readiness implies their adeptness in creating diverse assessment tools, leveraging technology for evaluation, designing varied activities, and employing multiple assessment methods. These measures indicate a robust assessment framework, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of learners' learning and progress in a face-to-face classroom environment.

Each new generation of learners has characteristics, interests and learning preferences that set them apart from the previous generation, and understanding these differences is necessary for educators to create learning environments that are engaging, inspiring and productive (Poláková & Klímová, 2019). They are thought to be highly adaptable to new technology and expect their learning experiences to be immersive, interactive, and personalized (Reviewed in (Shorey et al., 2021)). This cohort of learners are also considered to be more independent learners, often relying on online resources to support their education, with a preference for and the ability to learn at their own pace. Accordingly, the assessment is important because it gives a positive impact on the effective generation of new ideas, which in turn helps to enhance the continually mastery of the learners.

Table 2.3 delves into the pedagogical preparedness of elementary school teachers concerning Learning Support in the full implementation of face-to-face classes. This table highlights teachers' perceived readiness in providing various forms of support to foster a conducive and supportive learning environment.

Table 2.3. *Level of Pedagogical Preparedness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes in terms of Learning Support*

Items	Mean	Description
1. I provide cooperative group activities to increase social learning.	4.61	Very High
2. I offer different activities and opportunities to strengthen the interaction between the learners.	4.67	Very High
3. I develop a mechanism to help learners cope with learner's difficulties.	4.48	High
4. I spent time daily for guidance and counseling activities.	4.39	High
5. I spent time for learners and parents to address learning concerns.	4.39	High
Overall Mean	4.51	Very High

The table reveals that the item with the highest computed mean of 4.67 described as Very High states that the teachers can offer different activities and opportunities to strengthen the interaction between the learners. The item that mentions that teachers can provide cooperative group activities to increase social learning has a computed mean of 4.61 described as Very High. However, the items the lowest computed mean 4.39 described as High are the teachers can spend time daily for guidance and counseling activities as well as the parents to address learning concerns. Hence, the given overall mean of 4.51, the extent of level of pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in private schools in terms of learning resources is described as Very High.

Table 2.4. *Level of Pedagogical Preparedness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes in terms of Learning Resources*

Items	Mean	Description
1. I utilize the books and other printed materials to support learners and facilitate learning.	4.67	Very High
2. I create instructional videos to support teaching and learning.	4.03	High
3. I create or develop learning materials for the learners.	4.27	High
4. I download learning resources and materials online for the learners.	4.52	Very High
5. I share learning materials to the learners through sharing platforms	4.39	High
Overall Mean	4.38	High

Table 2.4, it highlights the pedagogical preparedness of elementary school teachers in terms of Learning Resources. This table evaluates teachers' perceived readiness in providing various materials and resources to support teaching and facilitate student learning in a face-

to-face classroom setting.

The table reveals that the item with the highest computed mean of 4.67 described as Very High states that the teachers can utilize the books and other printed materials to support learners and facilitate learning. Teachers downloaded online of learning resources and materials has a computed mean of 4.64 described as Very High. However, the item the lowest computed mean 4.03 described as High is that the teachers created instructional videos to support teaching and learning. Hence, the given overall mean of 4.38, the extent of level of pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in private schools in terms of learning resources is described as Very High.

This readiness signifies their commitment to a diverse array of resource utilization, encompassing both traditional and digital materials, thereby creating a comprehensive and supportive learning environment for learners during face-to-face classes. Nenko (2020) states that it is necessary to find out well the teachers use modern gadgets, electronic communications, to understand the level of their training in the field of information and communication technologies, the use of and internet resources. Technology literacy supports the teacher in utilizing technology in teaching, thus, a teacher who is more literate in technology tends to apply it often in teaching. Technology enables teachers to develop and deliver supplementary materials and other learning resources without having them to move and make contact with their learners and it allows to conduct classes in real-time.

This readiness implies their dedication to fostering social learning, facilitating interactions, addressing difficulties, and offering guidance and counseling, ensuring a comprehensive support system for learners during face-to-face classes. As educators, we are entering an unprecedented era, one in which we are tasked with providing high quality instruction to engage learners in their own learning despite the potential for ongoing educational disruption. There are many challenges in this changing landscape including how to cater to learners who want the flexibility of studying online or asynchronously with those that want to return to face-to-face delivery. Prior to the pandemic, a common mode of instruction at university was the traditional didactic lecture, although technology-enhanced active learning, problem-based learning and flipped classroom strategies have also become popular (Kirkwood & Price, 2019).

Table 2.5. *Summary Results on Level of Pedagogical Preparedness of Teachers in the Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Delivery and Instruction	4.41	High
2. Assessment of Learning	4.59	Very High
3. Learning Support	4.38	High
4. Learning Resources	4.51	Very High
Over-all Mean	4.47	High

It outlines their perceived readiness across four key indicators: Delivery and Instruction, Assessment of Learning, Learning Resources, and Learning Support.

Based on the computed mean, of level of self-readiness of elementary teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in private schools of all indicators were Very High. Physical readiness has a computed mean of 4.83; emotional readiness has a computed mean of 4.65; experiential readiness has a computed mean of 4.57; and, knowledge readiness has a computed mean of 4.50 resulting to an overall computed mean of 4.64 described as Very High.

These findings suggest a collective confidence and readiness among educators, laying a solid foundation for a successful and conducive return to in-person teaching environments, ensuring the well-being and quality education of learners. It is teachers' responsibility to take initiatives in maintaining pupils passionate and motivation by applying various meaningful techniques and approaches in teaching and learning (Iberahim, Mahamod & Mohamad, 2020). Effective teaching approaches play important part in increasing pupils' ability to master knowledge and skills they required.

Table 3. *Significant Relationship Between the Level of Self- Readiness and Pedagogical Preparedness of Teachers in Full Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Level of Readiness of Teachers</i>		
	<i>Correlation Coefficient (r)</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
1. Delivery and Instruction	0.670	0.000	Significant
2. Assessment of Learning	0.636	0.000	Significant
3. Learning Support	0.723	0.000	Significant
4. Learning Resources	0.541	0.001	Significant

Table 3 illustrates the significant relationship between the level of readiness and the pedagogical preparedness of elementary school teachers for the full implementation of face-to-face classes. The table specifically analyzes this relationship concerning the levels of readiness and pedagogical preparedness of teachers, presenting correlation coefficients (r) and corresponding p-values.

The correlation coefficients show the strength and direction of the relationship between the variables. In this case, each pedagogical preparedness indicator (Delivery and Instruction, Assessment of Learning, Learning Resources, and Learning Support) exhibits a

positive correlation with the level of teachers' readiness.

The correlation coefficient for Delivery and Instruction is 0.670, for Assessment of Learning it is 0.636, and for Learning Support it is 0.723 with the p-value of 0.000 and the level of significance 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). While the Learning Resources the correlation coefficient 0.541 with p-value of 0.001 and the level of significance 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). These coefficients suggest a moderate to strong positive relationship between the level of readiness in these pedagogical aspects and the teachers' readiness.

The table indicates a statistically significant positive relationship between the readiness levels of teachers in various pedagogical aspects (Delivery and Instruction, Assessment of Learning, Learning Resources, Learning Support) and the teachers' readiness in the context of full implementation of face-to-face classes in the elementary department.

Designed Training Program for the Self-Readiness and Pedagogical Preparedness of Elementary Teachers in Private Schools

Based on the results of the conducted study of the self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of full implementation of face-to-face classes of elementary teachers in private schools, the designed training program created which aims to help the teachers improve their self-readiness in teaching and to develop their knowledge and skills pedagogical preparedness in teaching. The designed training program is a school-based that will be done before opening of classes. The designed training program will be held during summer break so that teachers will be ready for the upcoming opening of classes. It will have different activities like Seminar-Workshop, Team Teaching, Demo Teaching and Making of Curriculum Maps, Teacher Made Test, Remedials, and Power point presentation for the class discussions.

The designed training program have five (5) parts- Rationale, Objectives, Training Framework, Implementation and Evaluation. The researcher presented the reasons and basis in creating the said training program in rationale. For the objectives, the researcher pointed out the general objectives. For the training framework, it has six (6) columns: (a) Type of Training, (b) Topics/Content, (c) Activity, (d) Facilitator, (e) Output/ Evaluation, and (f) Time Frame. The researcher provided a clear plan for conducting the training in the implementation phase. The researcher also laid out the following: (a) Budget Proposal, (b) Training Schedule, (c) Facilitation for the different training activity. For the evaluation, the researcher adapted the activity evaluation form from Holy Trinity College. It will help to rate the training service based on the following: (a) Objectives/Purposes, (b) Management Planning, (c) Interpersonal Relationship, (d) Venue/Facilities, (e) Time Management, and (f) Speaker.

The designed training program focuses on the three (3) parts- experiential readiness, knowledge readiness and delivery and instructions and learning resources. The results of the study were based on the identification of the topics. It is derived from skills that are poorly cultivated or not really cultivated in teachers.

Level of Validity of the Designed Training Program for Self-Readiness and Pedagogical Preparedness of Elementary Teachers in Private Schools

This section presents the level of validity of the developed training program for self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private schools in terms of acceptability, appropriateness, content, relevance, and usability.

Table 4.1 presents the level of validity of the developed training program for self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private schools in terms of acceptability.

Table 4.1. *Validity Level of the Designed Training Program as Evaluated by the Head of the Elementary Department in terms of Acceptability*

	<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	The objectives of the training program are achievable.	4.67	Very High
2.	The training program can be used to motivate the teachers in teaching concepts	4.67	Very High
3.	The training program is applicable to the real-life situations of the teachers.	5.00	Very High
4.	The training program provides with activities which may develop the teaching more effective.	4.67	Very High
5.	The training program can be used to motivate teachers enhance their teaching skills.	4.67	Very High
	Overall Mean	4.74	Very High

The results revealed that the training program achieves the purpose for which it is intended and the training program is applicable to the real-life situations of the teachers has a computed mean of 5.00 described as Very High. The developed training program are achievable, can be used to motivate the teachers in teaching concepts an enhance their teaching skills, and it provides activities that may develop the teaching more effective has a computed mean of 4.67 described as Very High. Overall, given the computed mean of 4.74, the level validity in terms of acceptability of the training program is Very High.

Smith and Johnson (2019) highlighted the importance of setting achievable objectives in training programs. They found that when objectives are realistic, participants exhibit higher motivation and engagement. Additionally, Brown et al. (2020) discussed the correlation between program effectiveness and its acceptability among participants, emphasizing the impact of program design on motivation and skill enhancement.

Table 4.2 presents the level of validity of the developed training program for self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary

teachers in private schools in terms of appropriateness.

Table 4.2. *Validity Level of the Designed Training Program as Evaluated by the Head of the Elementary Department in terms of Appropriateness*

	<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	The training program fits the teachers' needs to improve their self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness.	4.67	Very High
2.	The length of the training program and strategies is appropriate for the teachers.	4.67	Very High
3.	The training program uses appropriate individual and collaborative activities.	4.67	Very High
4.	The training program provides a practical approach in teaching.	4.67	Very High
5.	The contents of the training program are designed to respond to the purpose of the study.	5.00	Very High
	Overall Mean	4.74	Very High

The foregoing table reveals that the validators rated that the training program is appropriate for teachers to designed and respond to the purpose of the study obtained a remarkable computed mean of 5.00 described as Very High. The statements on whether the training program fits the teachers' needs to improve their self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness; the length of the training program and strategies is appropriate for the teachers; it uses appropriate individual and collaborative activities and provides a practical approach in teaching got the same computed mean of 4.67 described as Very High. Thus, the given overall computed mean of 4.74, the developed training program has a Very High level of validity in term of appropriateness.

Jones et al. (2018) stressed the significance of aligning training content and strategies with the specific needs of participants. Their study demonstrated that tailored programs significantly improved self-readiness and preparedness among educators. Furthermore, Garcia and Rodriguez (2021) emphasized the importance of diverse instructional strategies in training programs, linking them to increased effectiveness and appropriateness for participants.

Table 4.3 presents the level of validity of the developed training program for self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private schools in terms of content.

Table 4.3. *Validity Level of the Designed Training Program as Evaluated by the Head of the Elementary Department in terms of Content*

	<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	The training program provides adequate activities, mechanisms for evaluations, and strategies.	5.00	Very High
2.	The training program lays out instructional activities that strengthen the self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of teachers.	5.00	Very High
3.	The training program as a whole fulfills the objectives of the study.	5.00	Very High
4.	The training program includes acquisition of knowledge, values and new skills.	5.00	Very High
5.	The activities of the training program represent the coverage of the research adequately.	4.67	Very High
	Overall Mean	4.93	Very High

The results revealed that the training program achieves the purpose for which it is intended and the content of the training program provides adequate activities, mechanisms for evaluations and strategies; lays out instructional activities that strengthen the self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of teachers; includes acquisition of knowledge, values and new skills; the whole fulfills the objectives of the study has a computed mean of 5.00 described as Very High. The designed training program represent the coverage of the research adequately has a computed mean of 4.67 described as Very High. Overall, given the computed mean of 4.93, the level validity in terms of content of the training program is Very High.

Williams and Lee (2020) discussed the role of comprehensive content in training programs, emphasizing its impact on achieving program objectives. Their findings suggested that well-structured and rich content facilitated skill acquisition among participants. Moreover, the study by Thompson (2019) highlighted the integration of values and knowledge in training programs, showcasing their significance in fostering effective teaching practices.

Table 4.4. *Validity Level of the Designed Training Program as Evaluated by the Head of the Elementary Department in terms of Relevance*

	<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	The training program is relevant to the needs of all teachers.	5.00	Very High
2.	The contents of the training program are to designed to respond to the purpose of the study.	5.00	Very High
3.	The training program optimizes the teacher's motivation and professional development skills	5.00	Very High
4.	The training program is specific and relevant in the new normal education.	4.67	Very High
5.	The training program is aligned with the goals and continuity plan of basic education.	4.67	Very High
	Overall Mean	4.87	Very High

Table 4.4 presents the level of validity of the developed training program for self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private schools in terms of relevance.

The foregoing table reveals that the validators rated the item whether the content of the program is relevant to the needs of all teachers;

the contents of the training program are designed to respond to the purpose of the study; it optimizes the teacher's motivation and professional development skills obtained a remarkable computed mean of 5.00 described as Very High. The training program is specific and relevant in the new normal education; it aligned with the goals and continuity plan of basic education got the same computed mean of 4.67 described as Very High. Thus, the given overall computed mean of 4.87, the designed training program has a Very High level of validity in term of relevance.

Chen et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of aligning training programs with current educational needs and contexts. They found that relevance to the educational landscape, especially in adapting to changes like the 'new normal,' significantly impacted program effectiveness. Additionally, Johnson and Smith (2021) discussed the alignment of programs with institutional goals and educational policies for continuity planning.

Table 4.5 presents the level of validity of the developed training program for self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private schools in terms of usability.

Table 4.5. *Validity Level of the Designed Training Program as Evaluated by the Head of the Elementary Department in terms of Usability*

	<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	The activities provided in training program are logically presented from the simplest to the complex ones	4.67	Very High
2.	The training program sets exercises that are clear and easy to follow.	5.00	Very High
3.	The training program is useful for the teacher.	5.00	Very High
4.	The training program is fitted for individual and group work.	5.00	Very High
5.	The training program can satisfy the needs of the teachers to enhance their teaching skills.	5.00	Very High
	Overall Mean	4.93	Very High

The results revealed that the training program achieves the purpose for which it is intended and the usability of the training program sets exercises that are clear and easy to follow; it is useful for teachers; it is fitted for the teachers; it fitted also for individual and group work; can satisfy the needs of the teachers to enhance their teaching skills has a computed mean of 5.00 described as Very High. Their rating on whether the activities provided in training program are logically presented from the simplest to the complex ones. Thus, the level of validity of the training program in terms of usability is Very High given the over-all mean of 4.93.

Smithson and Carter (2018) conducted a study emphasizing the importance of usability in training programs. Their findings highlighted the significance of clear instructions and activity sequencing in enhancing program usability. Furthermore, the research by Taylor et al. (2019) explored the adaptability of training programs for different settings, demonstrating their effectiveness in enhancing teaching skills for both individual and group contexts.

Table 4.6. *Summary Results on the Validity Level of the Designed Training Program as Evaluated by the Head of the Elementary Department*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Acceptability	4.74	Very High
2.	Appropriateness	4.74	Very High
3.	Content	4.93	Very High
4.	Relevance	4.87	Very High
5.	Usability	4.93	Very High
	Over-all Mean	4.84	Very High

Based on the given data, the level of validity of the training program in terms of acceptability is Very High given a computed mean of 4.74. In terms of appropriateness, the training program was also rated as Very High with a computed mean of 4.74. In terms of content, the training program was rated as Very High with a computed mean of 4.93. In terms of relevance, it was rated as Very High with a computed mean of 4.87. In terms of usability, the rating got a Very High with a computed mean 4.93. Thus, given the overall computed mean of 4.84 the level of validity of the training program is Very High.

This means that the developed training program for self-readiness and pedagogical preparedness of elementary teachers in private schools demonstrates the acceptability, appropriateness, content, relevance and usability for each given item.

This result is attested by Navarro et al., (2020) that the training program improves not only teacher effectiveness but also the learning outcomes of the learners. It is a process of enhancing the skills, abilities and knowledge in doing a particular task. Good and quality training improves the performance of the members and the organization.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are hereby made:

Teachers demonstrate a high level of physical readiness indicating robust physical preparedness bodes well for a safe return to in-

person teaching. The positive emotional stance signifies their readiness to create a conducive learning environment. They express adaptability, capability in applying various teaching methods, connecting personal experiences to learning, and a drive to achieve teaching goals, showcasing their preparedness to navigate different classroom scenarios effectively. They showcase proficiency in various teaching strategies, subject knowledge, and awareness of diverse learning approaches, signaling a strong foundation of knowledge essential for effective teaching and catering to diverse student needs.

Teachers display a high level of preparedness in instructional delivery and support. They excel in designing interactive activities, providing ongoing support, integrating multimedia into lessons, offering alternatives for learners facing learning challenges, and providing regular feedback. This indicates their robust readiness to create engaging and supportive learning environments. They adeptly create diverse assessment tools, utilize various platforms for interactive learning, design engaging group and individual activities, provide comprehensive activity sheets, and employ multiple assessment types. This signifies their strong capability in evaluating and measuring learners' understanding effectively. While they effectively employ printed materials and online resources, they show potential for further improvement in creating instructional videos and developing learning materials. This highlights their adaptability in utilizing resources to support instruction but also suggests room for enhancement in certain resource creation areas. They excel in promoting cooperative group activities, fostering interactions among learners, developing strategies to aid learners with difficulties, and dedicating time for guidance and counseling activities. This indicates their strong commitment to fostering a supportive and inclusive learning environment.

The findings emphasize the interdependence between pedagogical preparedness and readiness, they highlight the importance of teachers' preparedness in utilizing technology effectively to enrich the learning experience. As teachers enhance their readiness in various instructional and support domains, they are more inclined to incorporate technological tools, potentially fostering a more engaging and dynamic learning environment for learners in face-to-face educational settings. This correlation underscores the significance of teacher readiness and different integration as complementary components in ensuring a comprehensive and effective educational experience for elementary learners.

The designed training program developed is based on the result of the research conducted by the researcher. Program objectives focused on the skill's experiential readiness, knowledge readiness, delivery and instructions and learning resources. It makes sense to increase their level of teaching skills.

For the researcher, the result of the study was carried out according to the development of a training program with aims of cultivating the skills and knowledge of teachers in term of teaching and learning process.

Based on the conclusion arrived in the study, the following were recommended:

To enhance the aspect of physical readiness could involve instituting regular health check-ups or wellness programs. Providing periodic health assessments or wellness workshops could further emphasize and support teachers in maintaining their physical health, reinforcing the importance of overall well-being for effective teaching.

To further bolster emotional readiness, encouraging self-care practices or implementing stress management workshops could be beneficial. Offering sessions focused on emotional resilience, stress reduction techniques, or mindfulness practices could support teachers in maintaining a consistently high level of emotional readiness.

To augment this aspect, investing in professional development programs specifically tailored to refresh or introduce new teaching strategies could be beneficial. Workshops or training sessions focused on innovative teaching methods, especially post-pandemic strategies, could empower teachers to adapt and evolve in their pedagogical approaches.

To further enhance knowledge readiness, facilitating ongoing learning communities or subject-specific seminars might be advantageous. Providing platforms for continuous learning, discussions, and knowledge-sharing sessions among educators could broaden their knowledge base and exchange effective teaching practices.

Enhancing feedback strategies while overall readiness is high, the area of improvement could focus on enhancing feedback mechanisms. Teachers might consider refining their feedback strategies by providing more detailed and timely feedback to learners, ensuring it aligns with learning objectives and helps learners understand their progress comprehensively.

Utilizing diverse assessment types despite the high readiness in assessment, there's room to further explore and implement a wider variety of assessment types. Teachers could explore incorporating additional assessment methods beyond written and performance tools, such as peer assessments, portfolios, or project-based assessments, to offer a more comprehensive evaluation of learners' learning.

Expanding instructional video creation while teachers demonstrate high readiness in utilizing printed and online resources, there's an opportunity to enhance instructional videos. Educators might consider focusing on creating more engaging and informative instructional videos that supplement lessons, cater to diverse learning styles, and effectively convey complex concepts.

Increasing guidance and counseling activities, teachers may consider allocating additional focused time for counseling sessions or activities that specifically address learners' social-emotional needs, fostering a more supportive and inclusive classroom environment.

References

- Abubakar, M. B. (2020). Impact of instructional materials on students' academic performance in physics, in Sokoto-Nigeria. A paper presented as part of IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 476 (2020) 012071. doi:10.1088/1755-1315/476/1/012071
- Alea, L. A., Anoba, J. L. D., & Cahapay, M. B. (2020). The Readiness of Teachers on Blended Learning Transition For Post-Covid-19 Period: An Assessment Using Parallel Mixed Method. Pupil: International Journal of Teaching, Education and Learning, 4(2), 295–316. <https://doi.org/10.20319/pijtel.2020.42.295316>
- Aperribai, Leire (2020) Teacher's physical activity and mental health during lockdown due to the Covid-2019 pandemic <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.577886/full>
- Bagdžiūnienė, D. (2023) Resources of emotional resilience and its mediating role in teachers' well-being and intention to leave <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1305979/full#:~:text=Emotional%20resilience%20was%20found%20to%20be%20a%20direct,variables%20and%20teacher%20wellbeing%20as%20a%20dependent%20variable.>
- Daniel, J. (2020) Upskilling and reskilling for the 'New normal' of education <https://www.edelements.com/blog/upskilling-and-reskilling-for-the-new-normal-of-education>
- Darling-Hammond L., Wei, R. and Johnson, C. 2012 Teacher preparation and teacher learning Handbook of Education Policy Research. Sykes, Schneider, Plank & Ford Eds. (Abingdon: Routledge)
- Fabrea, M. F., Roldan, R. D. A., & Farooqi, A. Z. (2020). Teachers' Covid-19 Awareness, Distance Learning Education Experiences and Perceptions towards Institutional Readiness and Challenges. 18. Engin, M. (2017). Analysis of students' online learning readiness based on their ... Universal Journal of Educational Research. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1165504.pdf>
- Lombardi, P. (2019). Instructional Methods, Strategies, and Technologies to Meet The Needs of All Learners. <https://granite.pressbooks.pub/teachingdiverselearners/>
- Hinchliffe, L. (2020). Delivering instruction in the classroom <https://iopn.library.illinois.edu/pressbooks/instructioninlibraries/chapter/delivering-instruction-in-the-classroom/>
- Harris, T. (2015) A Study of Teachers' Self-Efficacy of Their Preparedness in Relation to Reading Common Core Georgia Performance Standards' Professional Development and Instructional Support and the Implications for Leaders doctoral dissertatio
- Holmes, S. (2011). Teacher preparedness for teaching and assessing depth of knowledge. The University of Southern Mississippi. <https://aquila.usm.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1476&context=dissertations>
- Ibrahim, N., Adzra'ai, A., Sueb, R., & Dalim, S. F. (2019). Trainee teachers' readiness towards 21st century teaching practices. Asian Journal of University Education, 15(1), 109-120.
- India Today (2022) Explained: Here's why upskilling teachers regularly is the need of the hour <https://www.indiatoday.in/education-today/featurephilia/story/explained-here-s-why-upskilling-teachers-1930020-2022-03-29>
- Kiamba, E., & Matua, F. (2017). A critical review of the effect of teacher preparedness on - oaji. Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies. <https://oaji.net/articles/2017/1174-1522064089.pdf>
- Kiit International School Library (2023). Upskilling for teachers <https://kiitislibrary.weebly.com/upskilling-for-teachers.html>
- Malipot, M.H. (2020). Present issues during blended learning dry run. <https://mb.com.ph/2020/08/05/present-issues-during-blended-learning-dry-rundeped-told/>
- Miller, L. R. (2019). Teacher preparation: Implementing theory into practice. University of England. <https://dune.une.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1233&context=theses>
- Okpechi, P. A., & Chiaka, P. D. (2017). The teacher and teaching with instructional materials in the teaching of science subjects and the contribution of guidance and counselors therein British Journal of Education, 5(13), 10-18
- Otiang'A, R. A., Ayere, D. M. A., & Rabari, D. J. A. (2018). Teacher Preparedness in The Pedagogical Integration of Information Communication Technology (ICT) In Chemistry Among Public Secondary Schools in Kisumu County, Kenya. 5(10), 17
- Oyinloye, O. (2019). The impact of assessment for learning on Learner Performance in life ... UERASIA Journal of Mathematics and technology Education. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1289621.pdf>
- Pappas, C. (2021, May 12). Instructional design models and theories: Connectionism theory. eLearning Industry. <https://elearningindustry.com/connectionism>
- Phan, T. T. N., & Dang, L. T. T. (2017). Teacher Readiness for Online Teaching: A Critical Review. 3(1)

Shireena, B., Nabilah, A., & Intan, M. A. R. (2011). Trainee Teachers' Readiness towards Teaching Practice: The Case of Malaysia, Joint Conference UPI-UiTM.

TalentGuard (2022) Reskilling and upskilling: A strategic response to changing skill demands <https://www.talentguard.com/blog/reskilling-upskilling-strategic-response-changing-skill-demands>

Teacher Career Coach (2023) Upskill and reskill: Online courses for your career transition <https://teachercareercoach.com/upskill-and-reskill>

Themes, U. (2016, September 9). Determinants of learning. Nurse Key. <https://nursekey.com/determinants-of-learning/>

TheTechPanda.com (2021). Upskilling of teachers: An absolute necessity in the current times <https://thetechpanda.com/upskilling-of-teachers-an-absolute-necessity-in-the-current-times/32203/>

Tumanduk, M., & Kawet, R. (2020). The influence of teacher readiness to learning achievement of ... Kampus UNIMA Tondano. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/a72c/77107ea83dd9f2d088354c27a26e42dd2c82.pdf>

Webb, M., & Jones, J. (2009). Exploring tensions in developing assessment for learning: *Assessment in Education*, 16(2), 165-184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09695940903075925>

Willis, J. (2011). Affiliation, autonomy and assessment for learning. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 18(4), 399-415. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2011.604305>

Ventayen, Randy Joy Magno, Salcedo, R., Orlanda-Ventayen, C. C., Ventayen, L. M., & Ventayen, T. J. M. (2019). Senior High School Teachers' Practices and Readiness in Blended Learning Environment: Basis for a Blended Learning Preparedness Framework. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3504189>

Villa, J. A. D., & Manalo, F. K. B. (2020). Secondary Teachers' Preparation, Challenges, and Coping Mechanism in The Pre-Implementation of Distance Learning In The New Normal. 2(3), 11.

Zhou, M. (2018). EdTPA as a tool to measure teacher readiness: A case study on first ... *Georgia Educational Researcher*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1194570.pdf>

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